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Review Article

MANAGEMENT OF SEPTIC SHOCK

Al-Hanuf Jamal Ahmed Al-Bokhari ¹, Fatmah Ibrahim AlAbdullah ², Hazem Faisal Alotaibi ³, Rohiya Emad Hejazi ³, Faris Matouq Almowalad ⁴, Adel Saleh Alanazi ⁵, Laila khalid alanazi ⁵, Nadiah Mohammadidris Ali Johar ³, Mohammed Abdullah Mohammed Asiri ⁶, Meshal Abdulrahman Hassan Ogran ⁷, Ahmad Abdulaziz M. Almehmadi ³

1- Umm-AlQura University ,2- Immam Abdurrahman bin Faisal University,3- Ibn sina National college,4- King Abdulaziz Hospital – Makkah,5- jordan University of Science and Technology,6- Prince Mansour Military Hospital , Taif,7- King Khalid University

Abstract:

Introduction: Sepsis is known as the systemic inflammatory response to infection. Sepsis is a very critical as it is seen in ten of thousand hospitalized patients and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) could develop in about thirty percent of these patients; mortality is observed in twenty percent of patients with sepsis and eighty percent of patients with septic shock. Early diagnosis and management are crucial because of very high mortality rates. Advances in the field of molecular biology have assisted us understand most pathologic events that occur in sepsis. Understanding sepsis pathogenesis is very critical in terms of new advancements in the diagnosis, follow-up, and management plan. The sepsis triad is systemic inflammation, coagulation, and disordered fibrinolysis. There are microbial pathogens and inflammatory responses included in the sepsis physiopathology. Researchers revealed that as a result of infection in tissues and traumatic damage, the humoral system was activated in the body and several cytokines were released. The end result is the systemic inflammatory response, hemostatic changes, and organ damage. Recently, studies have been conducted and concluded that describe the treatment of sepsis patients. Most of these methods' goals are to modulate or stop the sepsis physiopathology and prevent multiple organ failure. Many new methods have been reported to decrease mortality rates in severe sepsis. These involve the application of low tidal volume in acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), plasma glucose control, goal-oriented treatment started in the early period, and corticosteroid at mean doses. Besides medications, early and proper antibiotic treatment and cardiovascular support have huge importance in the management of sepsis.

Aim of work: In this review, we will discuss the management of septic shock

Methodology: We did a systematic search for the management of septic shock using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

Conclusions: Studies revealed that sepsis is a very critical disease globally. Recent studies that focused on unclarified mechanisms underlying sepsis provided new management approaches for physicians. Several management plans like balanced corticosteroid usage, antiendotoxin treatment, vasoactive agents such as levosimendan, HBO treatment, fibrates, and several antioxidant supplements are promising approaches for sepsis management. Due to the fact that there are several experimental and clinical studies, there is a need for further research to develop new treatment approaches.

Key words: management, septic shock, presentation, emergency.

Corresponding author:

Al-Hanuf Jamal Ahmed Al-Bokhari,
Umm-AlQura University

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INTRODUCTION:

Sepsis is known as the systemic inflammatory response to infection. Sepsis is a very critical as it is seen in ten of thousand hospitalized patients and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) could develop in about thirty percent of these patients; mortality is observed in twenty percent of patients with sepsis and eighty percent of patients with septic shock. Early diagnosis and management are crucial because of very high mortality rates ¹. Advances in the field of molecular biology have assisted us understand most pathologic events that occur in sepsis. Understanding sepsis pathogenesis is very critical in terms of new advancements in the diagnosis, follow-up, and management plan. The sepsis triad is systemic inflammation, coagulation, and disordered fibrinolysis. There are microbial pathogens and inflammatory responses included in the sepsis physiopathology. Researchers revealed that as a result of infection in tissues and traumatic damage, the humoral system was activated in the body and several cytokines were released. The end result is the systemic inflammatory response, hemostatic changes, and organ damage [2].

Recently, studies have been conducted and concluded that describe the treatment of sepsis patients. Most of these methods' goals are to modulate or stop the sepsis physiopathology and prevent multiple organ failure. Many new methods have been reported to decrease mortality rates in severe sepsis. These involve the application of low tidal volume in acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), plasma glucose control, goal-oriented treatment started in the early period, and corticosteroid at mean doses. Besides medications, early and proper antibiotic treatment and cardiovascular support have huge importance in the management of sepsis [3].

In this review, we will discuss the most recent evidence regarding the management of septic shock.

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for the management of

septic shock using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: management, septic shock, presentation, emergency.

Incidence and Causes

While a comparative reduction has been seen in the prevalence of sepsis in the population in the recent years, the rise in the number of hospital-based sepsis patients stands out. There is a gradual rise in the frequency of hospital-based sepsis. The increases in the advanced age group in the population, extension in the life cycles of patients with chronic disease, common use of immunosuppressive drugs, and common use of invasive procedures for diagnosis or treatment purposes increase the frequency of sepsis. Hospital-based sepsis is more often seen in hospitals with a higher bed capacity and intensive care units and where more invasive surgeries are done [4].

Clinical Features

The presence of clinical findings is often subtle. They can present as fever, mental fog, temporary hypotension, reduced urine amount, or unexplained thrombocytopenia. If necessary, management plan are not taken or if sepsis is not treated, respiratory and renal failure, coagulation disorders, and irremediable hypotension can develop [5]

Outcome

The mortality rate is very high in spite of new advancements in sepsis management. The mortality rate is believed to be between twenty and eighty percent. Different mortality rates have been reported in these studies depend on the fact that the study groups were heterogeneous. The mortality rate is fifty percent in gram-negative bacterial sepsis, thirty percent in gram-positive bacterial sepsis, and twenty percent in anaerobic sepsis [6]. The mortality rate varies between seventy and ninety percent when

shock, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), ARDS, and other organ failure complications develop.

Physiopathology

Sepsis has a complicated pathology, and it is not yet understood due to the fact that it has a variable clinical and physiopathological signs and symptoms [7].

Host response

Sepsis is well-defined as the excessive and abnormal response of the host against an existing infection [9]. After systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), i.e., an excessive proinflammatory condition, arises initially, compensatory anti-inflammatory response syndrome (CARS), i.e., an excessive anti-inflammatory condition, occurs. While SIRS results in shock-based mortality, immunosuppression in the advanced phase of CARS and sepsis lead to mortality due to secondary lethal infections. For years, it was thought that pathogen invasion is responsible for the damage seen in sepsis. But, today, it is clear that damage is substantially caused by an unnecessary uncontrolled host response [8].

It was noticed that the host is not passive in sepsis. The roles of indigenous inflammatory mediators in organ damage and noninfectious causes also lead to the same inflammatory response, and the clinical response can be continued even though the infection can be removed [9].

The most crucial factor in sepsis formation derives from the insufficiency of nonadaptive host factors. The decline in defense mechanisms protecting the host against infection paves the way for local or systemic infections. Host defense mechanisms consist of anatomic barriers, cellular immunity (phagocytic cells or lymphocytes), and specific and nonspecific humoral defenses [10].

Innate immunity

Macrophages, bacterial toxins such as lipopolysaccharides (LPSs), and proinflammatory cytokines are activated through the release of other mediators [11]. Pathogen-related molecular patterns in microorganisms, mainly antigen presenting cells, are recognized by receptors, which are called pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), found on the surface of the cells of the natural immune system [12].

Coagulation abnormalities

The role of coagulation in infection is to surround the infection and maintain the inflammatory response local. But, its extreme activation can lead to harmful

effects¹³. Most of the cytokines secreted from the cells in sepsis stimulate thrombin formation. The extrinsic pathway first and then the intrinsic coagulation system are activated with the factor XII activation. Fibrin thrombi occur in the microvascular bed and contribute to organ failure. Consuming coagulation proteins leads to bleeding, and this is seen with both bleeding and thrombus development in the patients. While fibrin is fragmented by the plasmin, which results in fibrinolysis. Defined as DIC, it is one of the most crucial reasons for the poor prognosis of sepsis.

Organ dysfunction

Typically, multiple organ failures occurs in sepsis patients, and patients often die. While firstly single organ failure develops in the patients, unless the sepsis origin is eradicated, multiple organ failure develops in the later phase. The death risk increases by twenty percent for each organ failure¹⁴. If there are 4 or 5 organ failures, the mortality rate goes above ninety percent.

Treatment

Successful management in sepsis is dependent on early diagnosis, immediately starting the proper antibiotic medication and supporting treatment, and removal of or recovery from the underlying disease. Protection is one of the most methods of decreasing morbidity and mortality rates. Most of the attacks are nosocomial.

Antibiotics are given empirically in most cases during the time until the the team can determine the involved microorganism. The first 6 hours are extremely crucial in terms of prognosis after the revelation of the sepsis symptoms and findings. It is known that the shock incidence is decreased by half with the appropriate antibiotic treatment no matter what the underlying disease is in sepsis developing from gram-negative bacteria.

The main objective in septic shock management is controlling blood volume and providing enough tissue perfusion and tissues. the first thing to accomplish is to provide an enough liquid treatment [11]. With the fluid treatment, vasoactive medications could be added to the treatment in the patients whose fluid deficit is met but they still have hypotension despite fifteen mm Hg “pulmonary wedge” pressure. Corticosteroids are another important agent shown to reduce death risk in sepsis treatment [15].

When necessary, organ-supporting therapies (respiratory failure and kidney failure treatments)

should be used in sepsis treatment. In specific, the load on respiratory muscles is reduced by timely intubation and mechanic ventilation, and sudden respiratory standstills are avoided.

Search for New Therapies

New approaches

It is clear that more precise factors are required for sepsis management, and sepsis definitions should be reconsidered. Yet recently, there have been studies published that explain the treatment of sepsis patients. Most of these methods aim to alter or interrupt the sepsis physiopathology and prevent multiple organ failure. While some studies are in the early phases of the advanced phases (TNF- α antibodies, bactericidal/permeability-increasing protein, high hemofiltration, platelet-activating factor, etc.), some other methods are in an the advanced phase, and they have begun to affect findings in ICU [16].

Many new methods for decreasing mortality rates in severe sepsis have been newly reported. These new approaches consist of Low tidal volume application, intense plasma glucose control in ARDS is a treatment for the target started in the earlier period, and corticosteroid treatment in mean doses.

Corticosteroids do not improve survival when applied in high dosages in sepsis treatment, and it is known that they lead to secondary infections due to their immunosuppressive effects and adversely affect the clinical progress in sepsis [15]. But, it was demonstrated that they decreased mortality rates when applied in low and high doses in the long term and shortened the shock period requiring use the vasopressor [17].

LPSs, which play a role as endotoxins during sepsis, are reduced by binding to LDLs and HDLs. It was seen that intense insulin application provided an increase in LDL and HDL levels, and it was claimed that this application could be a new method in sepsis treatment. Clinical studies remain to be conducted on other antiendotoxin treatments for sepsis [18].

CONCLUSIONS:

Studies revealed that sepsis is a very critical disease globally. Recent studies that focused on unclarified mechanisms underlying sepsis provided new management approaches for physicians. Several management plans like balanced corticosteroid usage, antiendotoxin treatment, vasoactive agents such as levosimendan, HBO treatment, fibrates, and several antioxidant supplements are promising approaches for sepsis management. Due to the fact that there are several experimental and clinical studies, there is a

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REFERENCES:

1. **Bone RC, Grodzin CJ, Balk RA.1997** Sepsis: a new hypothesis for pathogenesis of the disease process. *Chest* 1997; 112: 235-43.
2. **Cohen J.2002** The immunopathogenesis of sepsis. *Nature* 2002; 420: 885-91.
3. **Marx G, Schuerholz T, Reinhart K.2005** New approaches to intensive care for sepsis. *Chirurg* 2005; 76: 845-55.
4. **Pittet D, Li N, Woolson RF, Wenzel RP.1997** Microbiological factors influencing the outcome of nosocomial bloodstream infections: a 6-year validated, population-based model. *Clin Infect Dis* 1997; 24: 1068-78.
5. **Mermetluoglu C, Devenci O, Dayan S, Aslan E, Bozkurt F, Tekin R.2016** Antifungal susceptibility and risk factors in patients with candidemia. *Eurasian J Med* 2016;48:199-203.
6. **Uzun O, Akalin HE, Hayran M, Unal S.1992** Factors influencing prognosis in bacteremia due to gram-negative organisms: evaluation of 448 episodes in a Turkish university hospital. *Clin Infect Dis* 1992; 15: 866-73.
7. **Rittirsch D, Flierl MA, Ward PA.2008** Harmful molecular mechanisms in sepsis. *Nat Rev Immunol* 2008; 8: 776-87.
8. **Schouten M, Wiersinga WJ, Levi M, van der Poll T.2008** Inflammation, endothelium, and coagulation in sepsis. *J Leukoc Biol* 2008; 83: 536-45.
9. **Bone RC, Balk RA, Cerra FB, et al. Definitions for sepsis and organ failure and guidelines for the use Eurasian J Med 2017; 49: 53-8** Polat et al. Current Treatment Strategies for Sepsis• 57 of innovative therapies in sepsis. The ACCP/SCCM Consensus Confer.
10. **Sahin S. Sepsiste Suprafizyolojik Doz Steroid Tedavisinin Yeri, in Klinik Bakteriyoloji ve Enfeksiyon Hastalıkları Anabilim Dalı 2009,** Erciyes Üniversitesi Tıp Fakültesi.
11. **Tas G. Deneysel Rat Sepsis Modelinde Fenofibrat Tedavisinin Rolü, in Askeri Tıp Fakültesi İç Hastalıkları Bilim Dalı Başkanlığı 2010,** T.C. Genelkurmay Başkanlığı Gülhane Askeri Tıp Akademisi.
12. **Russell JA.2006** Management of sepsis. *N Engl J Med* 2006; 355: 1699-713.
13. **Yuzbasioglu Y, Duymaz H, Tanrikulu CS, et al.2016** Role of procalcitonin in evaluation of the severity of acute cholecystitis. *Eurasian J Med* 2016; 48: 162-6.
14. **Bone RC.1991** Gram-negative sepsis. Background, clinical features, and intervention.

- Chest 1991; 100: 802-8.
15. **Cronin L, Cook DJ, Carlet J, et al.1995** Corticosteroid treatment for sepsis: a critical appraisal and meta-analysis of the literature. Crit Care Med 1995; 23: 1430-9.
 16. **Cheng B, Hoefl AH, Book M, Shu Q, Pastores SM.2015** Sepsis: pathogenesis, biomarkers, and treatment. Biomed Res Int 2015; 2015: 846935.
 17. **Polderman KH, Girbes AR.2004** Drug intervention trials in sepsis: divergent results. Lancet 2004; 363: 1721-3.
 18. **Reinhart K, Meier-Hellmann A, Beale R, et al.2004** Open randomized phase II trial of an extracorporeal endotoxin adsorber in suspected Gram-negative sepsis. Crit Care Med 2004; 32: 1662-8.